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IODINE DEFICIENCY AS A RISK FACTOR FOR HEALTH DISORDERS IN THE POPULATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS IN THE POST- CHERNOBYL PERIOD

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Annotation: Based on the analysis of the prevalence of iodine deficiency diseases in the post-Chernobyl period in the population of the Republic of Belarus, it is concluded that the indicators of primary incidence of diseases of the endocrine system in the post-Chernobyl period continue to remain high. Higher rates of primary morbidity of the population were noted in the Brest, Grodno, Vitebsk, Mogilev regions. The greatest increase in the primary incidence of endocrine diseases was detected in the Brest region.

Keywords: iodine deficiency, primary morbidity, post-Chernobyl period

ЙОДОДЕФИЦИТ КАК ФАКТОР РИСКА НАРУШЕНИЯ ЗДОРОВЬЯ У НАСЕЛЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ В ПОСТЧЕРНОБЫЛЬСКИЙ ПЕРИОД

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Аннотация: На основании анализа распространенности йододефицитных заболеваний в постчернобыльский период у населения Республики Беларусь сделаны выводы о том, что показатели первичной заболеваемости болезнями эндокринной системы в постчернобыльский

период продолжают оставаться высокими. Более высокие показатели первичной заболеваемости населения отмечены в Брестской, Гродненской, Витебской, Могилевской областях. Наибольший рост показателей первичной заболеваемости эндокринными заболеваниями выявлен в Брестской области.

Ключевые слова: йододефицит, первичная заболеваемость, постчернобыльский период

Relevance. Iodine deficiency is an urgent problem both in the medical field and in the social aspect. Iodine is necessary for the synthesis and production of thyroid hormones: triiodothyronine and thyroxine. Iodine-containing hormones provide physiologically full-fledged development and normal functioning of the whole organism as a whole. Through cytoplasmic receptors, the hormone acts on the chromatin of the nucleus, resulting in increased synthesis of nucleic acids (DNA, mRNA) and protein. The development of new protein molecules accelerates the growth, division and differentiation of cells, which is especially important for a growing organism and various regenerative processes. Thyroid hormones activate energy metabolism, i.e. the expenditure and synthesis of ATP. Since two oppositely directed processes are activated simultaneously, an equilibrium is maintained between them. Externally, this is manifested by an increase in oxygen consumption by tissues and the formation of heat to maintain normal body temperature.

The distribution of iodine in the environment is uneven, which is a consequence of the development of urban areas, various natural processes and other reasons. The territory of the Republic of Belarus is characterized by iodine deficiency, which negatively affects the health of the population and exacerbates radiation risks [1-4].

The accident at the Chernobyl nuclear power plant was the largest radiation accident in the history of humanity. The incidence of endocrine diseases in evacuated adults and adolescents increased 5.7 times in the mid-1990s. The exposure doses of the population were caused by emissions from the reactor of radionuclides iodine-131, caesium-134 and caesium-137. Radioactive iodine is concentrated mainly in the thyroid gland. The accumulation of radioactive iodine is especially dangerous when there is insufficient stable iodine in the body [1, 2].

Purpose. Analysis of iodine deficiency diseases in the post-Chernobyl period in the population of the Republic of Belarus.

Materials and methods of a research. The work uses epidemiological, search, comparative-evaluation, analytical methods. The official statistical data of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Belarus and the data of the state statistical reporting served as the material for study and analysis [1, 2, 6].

Results and discussion. Iodine deficiency (iodine deficiency diseases) are diseases associated with insufficient intake of iodine into the body [3-5]. It occurs as a result of: low iodine content in food; selenium deficiency, which refers to iodine synergists (with a lack of selenium, iodine is not absorbed by the body); according to research results, the cause of the development of endemic cretinism of newborns is a combined lack of iodine and selenium; radiation exposure; an increase in the content of goitrogens in the blood plasma (such as goitrogens, strumogens); tobacco smoking; alcohol abuse (ethanol reduces the iodine content in the body).

The severity of iodine deficiency is also influenced by gender (women have a higher risk of iodine deficiency than men) and age (different types of iodine deficiency may occur at different ages) [1, 3].

The human body cannot exist without iodine, as well as without water. We get iodine only from the outside: 90 % with food, and the rest with water and air. The thyroid gland is the most iodine-saturated organ. For its normal activity, an adult needs about 150 mcg, the maximum allowable amount of consumption is 300 mcg, and during pregnancy and lactation, the norm increases to 175-200 mcg. Iodine deficiency mainly has a negative effect on the functioning of the thyroid gland, which uses iodine to synthesize its hormones [3, 4].

In the first period after the Chernobyl disaster, a significant increase in the power of the exposure dose of gamma radiation was recorded almost throughout the territory of Belarus. The volume of available experimental data on measurements of iodine-131 activity in precipitation is limited, which required the development of special approaches to the reconstruction of radioactive contamination with iodine.

It is known that during the Chernobyl accident, all the iodine-131 accumulated in the nuclear reactor was released into the environment with an explosion, which led to severe radioactive contamination of the territory with a radius of 30 kilometers. Unfavorable climatic conditions, strong winds and rains spread radiation around the world, but the territories of such countries as Ukraine, Belarus, the Russian Federation, Finland, Sweden, Germany, and the United Kingdom were particularly affected [1].

The consequences of the iodine shock for the population in connection with the accident at the Chernobyl nuclear power plant was that the collective dose of thyroid radiation in the residents of Belarus during the iodine period amounted to more than 500 thousand people.-Gr. For persons under the age of 7, it has reached 130 thousand people.-Gr, 7-17 years – 80 thousand people-Gr and for adults – 300 thousand people-Gr. The irradiation of the thyroid gland continues even after the iodine period, albeit in much smaller doses due to the external and internal effects of radioactive cesium. During the post-accident period, the

collective dose of thyroid radiation due to radioactive cesium in residents of the Republic of Belarus amounted to more than 21 thousand people.-Gr [1].

The Gomel and Mogilev regions, 6 districts of the Brest region, 6 districts of Grodno and 1 district of Vitebsk were completely exposed to radioactive contamination. The highest levels of iodine-131 precipitation occurred in the near zone of the Chernobyl nuclear power plant, in the Braginsky, Khoiniksky, Narovlyansky districts of the Gomel region, where its content in soils amounted to 37,000 kBq/m² or more. In Chechersk, Kormyansky, Buda-Koshelevsky, Dobrushsky districts, pollution levels reached 18,500 kBq/m². The southwestern regions – Yelsky, Lelchitsky, Zhitkovichi, Petrikovsky districts of the Gomel region, as well as Pinsky, Luninetsky, Stolinsky districts of the Brest region were also significantly polluted. High levels of pollution also occurred in the north of the Gomel and Mogilev regions. In the Vetkovsky district of the Gomel region, the content of iodine-131 in the soil reached 20,000 kBq/m². In the Mogilev region, the greatest pollution was observed in the Cherikovsky and Krasnopol'sky districts (5550-11100 kBq/m²).

Children and teenagers, especially children under the age of 7, were the most exposed residents of Belarus in the radioactively contaminated territories. The results of direct measurements in 1986 showed that about 30 % of children under the age of 2 years received doses above 1 Gy. In the most polluted rural settlements, the average doses of thyroid radiation to younger children reached 3 Gy or more. The collective dose of thyroid radiation in the residents of Belarus in the "iodine" period amounted to more than 500 thousand people-Gr.

Conclusions. Thus, based on the study, analysis and systematization of official statistical data, it can be concluded that the indicators of primary morbidity of the population with diseases of the endocrine system in the post-Chernobyl period continue to remain high. There is an annual increase in endocrine diseases among the population throughout the country. Higher rates of primary morbidity of the population were noted in the Brest, Grodno, Vitebsk, Mogilev regions. The greatest increase in the primary incidence of endocrine diseases was detected in the Brest region.

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